

Modelling Least-Cost Decarbonisation Pathways in Ecuador's Energy System

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Energy Modelling Platform for Latin America and The Caribbean (EMP-LAC)

70%+
HYDROPOWER
Vulnerable to drought

30.07
CO₂ EMISSIONS
Energy Sector: Up 88% by 2050

29 MW
SOLAR CAPACITY
Potential: 33,750 MW

BAU

What if no new policies are implemented by 2050?

SOL-BAT

Can solar and batteries fully replace fossil fuels?

EMI-NDC

What is the absolute minimum cost to meet the NDC 3.0 target?

COST MINIMIZATION with physical and policy constraints.

TIMEFRAME: 2022 TO 2050

BAU (BUSINESS-AS-USUAL)

CONTINUATION OF HISTORICAL TRENDS

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NO NEW POLICIES

SOL-BAT (SOLAR & BATTERIES)

SOLAR DEPLOYMENT MANDATE
(to 6 GW)

BATTERY DEPLOYMENT MANDATE
NO EMISSION CAPS

 ENERGY TRANSITION

EMI-NDC (CO₂ EMISSION CAP)

LEGAL CO₂ CAP (aligned to NDC 3.0)

FREE TECHNOLOGY CHOICE

56.6 MTon

BAU 2050
+88% vs 2022 Not compliant with NDC

50.2 MTon

SOL-BAT 2050
+67% vs 2022

9.60 MTon

EMI-NDC 2050
-68% vs. 2022 ✓ NDC

Results: CO₂ Emission Trajectories, Ecuador 2022-2050

123.9 PJ

Hydro
BAU 2050

134.7 PJ

Solar PV
EMI-NDC 2050

0 PJ

Fossil fuel
EMI-NDC 2045

(a) BAU

(b) SOL-BAT

(c) EMI-NDC

~1,080×

Growth factor
2022 → 2050

31.3 GW

EMI-NDC 2050
(93% of potential)

USD 388/kW

Solar cost
by 2029 (IRENA)

Figure 3(a). Solar PV Installed Capacity by Scenario, 2022-2050 (GW)

>40 MTon

CO₂/yr from
biofuel blending

100%

Buses electric
by 2050 (EMI-NDC)

No H₂

H₂ not viable
in Ecuador 2022–2050

Figure 4. Transport sector activity by fuel type and scenario (PJ), 2022–2050.
(a) BAU / SOL-BAT (b) EMI-NDC

USD 277 M

Annual NDC cost
(vs BAU)

+6.1%

Total system cost
premium (EMI-NDC)

0.24% GDP

Affordable
(World Bank, 2024)

Figure 5. (a) Total discounted system cost 2022-2050 (M USD) and (b) annual capital investment by scenario.

(a) Total System Cost

(b) Annual Capital Investment

A binding CO₂ cap is the single most effective instrument

01

Only EMI-NDC achieves NDC 3.0 compliance (9.60 MTon CO₂-eq by 2050, -68%). This covers the energy sector (~34% of total GHG). Solar selects itself autonomously. Translate NDC into a legally enforceable annual emission limit.

02

Solar PV is the cheapest clean option : no mandate needed

USD 388/kW by 2029 (IRENA, 2025). 31.3 GW selected autonomously. Priority: streamline permits, expand grid, develop bankable projects. Cost above BAU: only USD 84 M over 28 years.

03

Transport electrification now : Ley 2025 is the foundation

BAU = SOL-BAT in transport. >40 MTon CO₂/yr from biofuels. Ley Orgánica Eficiencia Energética (2025): electric buses mandatory. EVs growing +140% in 2025 (AEADE).

References (9/9)

AEADE (2025) EV sales statistics Ecuador 2025. Quito. www.aeade.net

Cannone, C. et al. (2021) CCG Starter Data Kit — Ecuador. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5270965

Climate Analytics (2024) 1.5°C National Pathway Explorer — Ecuador. climateanalytics.org

MAATE (2025) NDC 3.0, period 2026–2035. Quito, Feb 2025. unfccc.int

Howells, M. et al. (2011) OSeMOSYS. Energy Policy 39(10):5850–5870. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033

IEA (2023) Net Zero by 2050. Paris. iea.org

IRENA (2025) Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2024. Abu Dhabi. ISBN: 978-92-9260-610-7

Ley Orgánica de Eficiencia Energética (2025) Registro Oficial Ecuador. Quito.

MAEE (2024) Plan Maestro de Electricidad 2023–2032. Quito. recursosyenergia.gob.ec

Pinchao, P. et al. (2024) Green H₂ from Hydropower in Ecuador. Energies 17(23):6051. doi: 10.3390/en17236051

Plazas-Nino, F.A. et al. (2022) National energy system optimization — Colombia. Energy 251:123950